

ISSUES OF DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH TERMINOLOGY IN AGRICULTURE

Saydamatova Nigora Sheraliyevna

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is the study and analysis of economic relations and problems of development of agrarian sector.

Agriculture around the world, including in Uzbekistan, is one of the most important sectors of the economy, which is aimed at providing the population with food, obtaining raw materials for other industries and developing domestic and foreign trade. This means that much depends on the level of development of agriculture: the quality of life and health of citizens, the functioning of such economic sectors as trade, industry, catering, etc.

Currently, the problems of economic growth and development of the country's agribusiness sector have become very topical, which is why theoretical and applied issues on this topic should be studied in more depth.

Over the last decade, this sector has been experiencing economic growth, but the lag with the development of the economy as a whole has not been overcome. Agriculture, which is dependent on natural factors and has a pronounced seasonal, cyclical nature of production, is adapting to changing economic and technological conditions more slowly than other sectors.

As Uzbek agriculture integrates into the global economy, an increasing degree of lagging of the domestic agricultural sector behind the world's leading food producers in all components of scientific and technological development becomes more and more tangible.

Financial instability of the sector, caused by instability of markets for agricultural products, raw materials and foodstuffs; shortage of qualified personnel, caused by low living standards and quality of life in rural areas; unfavorable general conditions of functioning of agriculture, first of all, unsatisfactory level of development of market infrastructure, which hinders access of agricultural producers to markets of financial, material, technical and informational resources, finished products - precisely because of these factors.

Agriculture - a branch of economy aimed at providing the population with food (food, nutrition) and obtaining raw materials for a number of industries [1]. As the most important link in the agro-industrial complex, agriculture differs from other sectors of the economy by its seasonal nature of production, use of land as a subject and means of labor, and strong

dependence on natural conditions. It consists of agriculture (crop production) and livestock production, which are closely related to each other and produce 56 and 44% of agricultural products, respectively.

Crop production includes the following segments: grain crops, pulses, fodder, technical, vegetable and citrus fruits, tonic, oily crops, as well as grape and horticultural crops. Animal husbandry includes the following elements (component parts - subsectors): cattle breeding, sheep breeding, horse breeding, rabbit breeding, aquaculture, poultry farming [1]. It is necessary to understand that the branches of agriculture in the country are undoubtedly connected with many scientific disciplines and methods, such as forestry, agronomy, etc. Therefore, the government should ensure the development of these areas of science in the country to enable scientists to develop new methods and ways to introduce agricultural business in the CIS countries and thus increase efficiency in this area of national economy.

The agricultural sector is of special importance in the country's economy. It is one of the main national economic sectors that determine the conditions for maintaining the vital activity of society. Its importance is not only in meeting people's needs for food, but also because it significantly affects employment and the efficiency of all national production [2].

State regulation of agriculture is a system of levers and incentives through which the state participates in market processes on the rights of the subject of market relations, ensuring the sustainable development of agro-industrial production.

The process of state regulation consists of a set of measures to ensure the implementation of laws introduced by government agencies to encourage or restrict economic activity.

Thus, the state support of agricultural production in developed Western countries is a powerful lever for economic and financial policy in agriculture. The mechanism of state regulation of agricultural production is characterized by a great diversity in the use of economic and financial instruments. That is why the experience of advanced agrarian countries is of great importance in the development of measures aimed at developing the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan.

In designing measures aimed at agricultural development, the experience of advanced agrarian countries is of great importance. Historically, there have been two main directions in Western agrarian policy: North American and Western European. The first direction was followed by the main exporters of food and agricultural raw materials (Canada, USA, Australia, and New Zealand), the second - by Western European countries, as well as Japan and some other food importing countries.

Nowadays the main content of agrarian policy of most economically developed countries is state support of agrarian sector by means of various subsidies, grants and privileges. In some countries, state financial investments in agriculture are 1.5-2 times higher than the market value of its products. State support to agriculture and food industry has played a major role in a sharp increase in food production in the countries that are currently its largest exporters: the USA, Canada, and EU countries [3].

In order to effectively use the means of state support of agriculture and effective state agrarian policy in the future it is advisable to consider the whole range of problems associated

with ensuring the achievement of targets and indicators of the State Program of Agricultural Development and Regulation of Markets of Agricultural Products, Raw Materials and Food.

Adequate social policy and promotion of a healthy lifestyle represents a village as an ecologically clean area for living, a source of income and the opportunity to develop their own business.

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